

What If Your PhD Turned Into a Nightmare?

I did not see it coming either...

"Shit happens" – said the Head of Department after I returned from the hospital – *"There are other universities too"*. – I was once a top Master's student and later a PhD candidate in Robotics at ETH Zürich. I experienced something that could have happened to any of us. What unfolded in just a few months, changed my life forever.

Dear Reader, I have no intention of taking too much of Your time. However, my story may be relevant to You, since we were once in the same boat. I don't want an incident like mine happening to You next. In case you don't want to read such a long letter, please jump to the "Conclusion" part for a quick glance. Otherwise, I hope you find my letter as thought-provoking, eye-opening, insightful, or maybe even as helpful or relatable as I intended.

Introduction

Since beginning my higher education, I have consciously prepared for an academic career, steadily developing my skills and profile. I earned my Master's in Robotics at ETH with outstanding and highly competitive results, ranking among the top 10 in my program. Beyond coursework, I successfully contributed to research projects and worked as a Teaching Assistant, consistently receiving top marks and positive feedback from my supervisors. Given my strong academic record and passion for research, I naturally applied to ETH laboratories for a PhD position. I quickly received an offer from the same lab where I completed my Master's thesis and was eager to begin my doctoral studies. Little did I know, this would soon turn out to be the objectively worst decision of my life.

I began my work during the final months of the COVID-19 pandemic, which naturally limited contact with my supervisors. My main supervisor, Dr. ι , headed the lab, while I had more frequent meetings and closer work relations with my direct supervisor, Dr. α . Starting the project was challenging, especially with the restrictions and the toll COVID-19 took on many of our mental health, including mine. Moreover, Dr. α was known to be difficult to work with and to create toxic work environments, which added to the strain. Still, I was determined to push through these obstacles.

Around this time, I suddenly experienced a huge and unexpected loss in my personal life, which left me grappling with overwhelming emotions and a deep sort of grief. While many people face such difficulties at some point in their lives, my situation seemed to be more serious. I experienced an episode of severe depression.

Consider the following: What image comes to mind when you think of depression?

Symptoms

Let's take a look at some of the symptoms I experienced [1]:

- Continuous and barely tolerable anxiety and fear for no apparent reason, making each day a deeply painful struggle.
- Rumination – being trapped in an unbreakable cycle of painful thoughts.
- Overwhelming pain that manifested as physical stomach aches.
- Persistent feelings of worthlessness and extreme guilt, with constant self-blame without any real reason.
- Panic attacks at least once a day.
- Dissociation – feeling detached from reality, like you are "not even there" as if observing life from the passenger seat.
- Severe deterioration in focus, decision-making, and memory – I could barely concentrate enough to do simple tasks, often feeling like being in a fog.
- Mood swings varying from deeply gloomy to sometimes seemingly ecstatic.
- Loss of interest in any activity, even the ones I once considered joyful or interesting.
- Sleeping over 12-14 hours daily, often during the afternoon – in order to escape the overwhelming burden of reality.
- Lack of eating – sometimes I didn't even notice, that I went 2 full days without eating anything.
- Crippling fatigue – even the simplest tasks seemed impossibly difficult to complete.
- Complete hopelessness – an inescapable, looming darkness that painted every vision of the future in despair.
- Daily, distressingly comforting thoughts of suicide, accompanied by recurring suicidal plans – this state is recognized as severe and dangerous.

The situation became really serious really quickly – within just one or two weeks. It was terrifying to witness my escalating symptoms, I had no idea what was happening to me. I was quickly losing the ability to function properly. My entire world was engulfed by this overwhelming state, and I felt powerless to stop it. I was sick, vulnerable, and in desperate need of external help. Despite this, I tried my best to keep going. I quickly reached out to my family, friends, and roommates, and sought professional help.

Coping strategies

Building effective coping mechanisms during a crisis like this is crucial but challenging. The first step is recogniz-

ing the problem and seeking professional help. Having previously dealt with anxiety, I reached out to a psychologist I knew from my home country. Speaking with a familiar therapist in my native language proved essential to my recovery. He quickly connected me with a psychiatrist to begin medication.

My second line of defense came from those close to me and the people in my everyday life. I opened up about my struggles in a delicate way, ensuring that I had enough people around me who were aware of my situation without putting too much pressure on anyone. Many felt grateful, even relieved, as my openness about my crisis encouraged them to share their own difficulties. These honest conversations quickly deepened existing relationships and fostered meaningful new friendships with colleagues, roommates, and peers.

Supervisor reactions

I had a conversation with my direct supervisor, Dr. α , where I explained that my personal life and health were temporarily affecting my performance. She seemed understanding at first, saying, *"Unexpected things can happen in life."* She reassured me that being slower in the first year of PhD wasn't a big issue and that I could make up for it in the second year. However, this understanding attitude quickly faded. Despite her initial words, she soon began pressuring me and criticizing my performance. Her behavior was often described by other colleagues as *"poking"* – she frequently engaged in micro-management and no matter what results her students presented, it never seemed to be enough to satisfy her. When I requested a meeting to discuss my condition, she initially refused but eventually agreed. As I tried to explain the seriousness of my health issues, she cut me off, saying, *"Other people have problems too."* and *"You need to work harder and prove you can do quality research."* Left with no other option, I pushed myself to the limit, which inevitably worsened my condition. I lost nearly all ability to work and eventually had to be hospitalized.

I later discovered that ETH Zürich offers an option for extended sick leave through Case Management. According to their website [2], supervisors are encouraged to take immediate action when an employee's health is at risk: *"If a member of your team is restricted in their ability to work or their health is under strain, you have a duty of care to take prompt action. As a manager, you have a key role in providing lasting support and to facilitate your employee's reintegration. Your HR Consulting team, which will liaise with Case Management, is happy to support you. Depending on the situation, you can also approach Case Management directly. Together we will discuss what further action to take."*

Finally, I approached Dr. ι about my health. As the head of the lab, he was extremely busy, and we mostly interacted through online meetings. Overall, we had a distant work relationship, making it difficult to bring up such matters. During our conversation, he expressed dissatisfaction with my performance for the first time

since I started my doctorate, saying he had doubts about my abilities. I explained that I was dealing with serious health issues that had significantly reduced my ability to work and that I might need hospitalization. I also mentioned the word *"depression"*. He became visibly frustrated and responded, *"This is not a stressful job."* From later conversations, I realized that he saw my condition neither as a serious health problem nor as a temporary setback. Instead, he viewed me as an unfit and problematic student, a burden on his lab.

In a subsequent meeting with Miss μ , the HR representative, I was informed that my work contract would not be renewed, but I was still allowed to remain in the PhD program under Dr. ι 's supervision. I was told I could take a few months to recover, after which we would have a discussion about my future at the lab. They also suggested that I use this period to reflect on whether I wanted to continue with my doctorate. Initially, I felt relieved and saw this as an opportunity for the unpaid medical leave I desperately needed. However, I later learned they didn't intend it that way – and I wasn't the only PhD student whose mental health concerns were handled similarly. In fact, at this point, by agreeing to this arrangement, I unwillingly gave up any work protection I might have had.

I would like to highlight some naturally arising important questions that may also be of public interest:

- How should students communicate with their supervisors when a health crisis affects their research performance?
- How should supervisors respond when informed about a student's health issues affecting their work?
- Who should take responsibility in such cases, and how should accountability be addressed?
- What solutions can or should research labs provide for early-career researchers facing similar health crises?

Recovery

I returned to my home country for a three-month hospital treatment program. During the first few weeks, I continued receiving emails from Dr. α , requesting unfinished results and code. I later heard rumors that she had told my colleagues I hadn't completed any code due to my inability to send it while I was undergoing treatment. Despite this, the therapy was highly effective, and I made a full recovery. My symptoms completely disappeared, and I felt like my old self again. This is a clear example that even severe mental health issues can be temporary and treatable, without the need for lifelong stigma. Unfortunately, my supervisors and higher-level ETH staff did not seem to share this perspective.

After returning from my successful medical leave, I had a conversation with Dr. ι about continuing my doctoral studies. It became immediately clear that he had never intended for me to return. I later found out that they had already consulted a student months earlier to

take my place. In his letter of resignation as my doctoral supervisor, he stated that *"the student no longer had an interest in the project."* I never said that.

I quickly found myself left hanging in the air. I hadn't received income for over months, I had just returned from the hospital having survived a serious illness, and I had been dismissed from a doctoral program without notice. Or, more specifically, with a negative notice period, essentially fired months before even being informed. My world shattered completely, and once again, I found myself in yet another crisis, even greater and more long-lasting than the illness itself. This sudden loss of security caused me to relapse into depression, making it nearly impossible to find a new position. With no money, my prospects of staying in Zürich were dim. The gap in my CV made me uncompetitive in Switzerland's job market, and with a discontinued PhD, securing another academic or research position seemed out of reach. I quickly realized just how stigmatizing such an incident can be for early career researchers. Career advisors suggested I should *"learn to lie"* and craft an alternative story to explain my discontinued doctorate and the gap in my career. During interviews with professors at other institutions, while my strong academic record was acknowledged, they often voiced concerns about my previous PhD interruption and the personal challenges behind it. The questions regarding my troubled past frequently led to rejections, plunging me into a deep sense of hopelessness and making me feel like an outcast, stigmatized in the academic community. It took years to rebuild my career and fully process what had happened.

Aftermath

I escalated my case by reaching out to Dr. λ , the head of the department overseeing my lab. As outlined in my PhD contract, I was entitled to a mediated meeting with my supervisors, conducted by the department head. However, the initial meeting, where only Dr. λ and Miss μ from HR were present, left me speechless and confused. The experience haunted me for years, leaving a lasting impact.

I had hoped for understanding or even a potential solution from the university. Instead, the response I received was far from what I expected. After hearing my story, Dr. λ remarked: *"shit happens"* and *"there are other universities too"* – implying that students struggling with issues like mine had no place at ETH Zürich. He further explained that it wasn't the supervisor's responsibility to handle such situations and that I should have provided a doctor's certificate specifically from a Swiss doctor – a requirement that, to this day, is not mentioned on ETH's case management or any other website [2]. When I pointed this out, Miss μ simply replied, *"the maintenance of the website is not our responsibility."* Miss μ added, *"You need to learn the rules of the country if you are coming to study or work here,"* and mentioned that since my contract ended before my sick leave, they were under

no obligation to renew it – information she had never communicated to me previously. I felt deceived, especially in such a vulnerable state. Despite my repeated requests, Dr. λ refused to arrange a mediated meeting, stating, I would only screw it up and it would make my situation worse. He also warned me against pursuing any formal action, saying, *"you don't want to make enemies in academia."* This sentence made me feel threatened and crushed by an infinitely larger power. He added that now I have a chance for a successful career, however, if I start a long legal fight, I will run out of time and opportunities – clearly understanding my difficult life and career situation, and my inability to defend myself.

I reached out to AVETH [3], and while my counselor was understanding and helpful, I quickly realized there was little they could do. They informed case management about the missing information on their website, but even after years, nothing changed. Although they presented my case alongside others during regular meetings with higher-level academic staff, I saw no response, no consequences, and no real change. From AVETH, I learned that my situation was not unique and that I should be careful. Professors tend to threaten students with legal consequences, and I probably have to accept the situation as it is. They've seen many cases where students suffered for years following an incident like mine and had to leave academia and/or Switzerland entirely.

I felt that despite my hard work during my studies, I suddenly became unwanted and an outcast. My only sin was falling ill temporarily, and no matter how hard I tried and even succeeded in recovering, it didn't matter. In time of need, the university extended its arm and crushed me with it. I felt banished, threatened, and stigmatized. Hopeless and powerless in the face of an infinitely larger force. I truly felt like a subhuman. Humiliated and ashamed, I found myself in a deep existential crisis.

The long-term consequences of this incident have been devastating. In just a few months, every aspect of my life collapsed, and the fruits of six years of hard work, dedication, and sacrifice were wiped out. I lost hope in continuing my career and achieving my goal of becoming a researcher and professor, a path I had worked so hard to pursue. Nothing could have prepared me for this. I always believed that if a health crisis occurred, there would be a safety net to catch me. Instead, I feel that the university took a serious yet manageable issue, and by taking advantage of my vulnerable state, they escalated it into a full-blown catastrophe. With just a little help and understanding – perhaps a few months of unpaid medical leave – this all could have been avoided.

It took me years to fully process the treatment I endured and the situation I found myself in. I spent years in therapy, struggling with financial instability while trying desperately to rebuild my career. However, staying competitive seemed nearly impossible given the circumstances. I often felt hopeless, angry, and at times, suicidal. Sleepless nights became common as I endlessly ruminated over the words my ETH supervisors and staff

had said to me. The stress following my dismissal also took a significant toll on my physical health. I quickly developed severe acid reflux and other stomach-related illnesses, all stemming from the overwhelming pressure I was suddenly under.

The struggle for understanding

In the following, I had several meetings with different levels of staff at ETH Zürich. First, I talked with the Vice Rector of the university, then I reached out to Respect ETH [4]. When I shared my story and expressed that I felt discriminated against due to my illness, the Vice Rector responded, *"There is no such thing as discrimination against mental health issues at ETH Zürich. We have done a lot in this regard."* She also added *"Your case is closed, there is not much we can do."* Respect ETH arranged a mediated meeting with my former supervisor, Dr. α . The outcome was that my supervisors did not fully understand the gravity of my situation, and I was told that I should have communicated more clearly. The official stance of Respect ETH was that the situation would have unfolded in the same way regardless of my supervisors' reaction and that early-career researchers at ETH Zürich cannot afford a prolonged or serious illness without the risk of losing their position. A few weeks later, Dr. α left the university to take up an assistant professor role at another institution.

This marked the point when I reached out to the local Ombuds Office at ETH Zürich [5]. With their assistance, I arranged a mediated meeting with my main supervisor, Dr. ι , who insisted that Miss μ also be present. Before the meeting, I unexpectedly encountered Miss μ in the corridor, and she remarked, *"Now I understand that you were really sick."* – revealing that, until then, she had not understood and handled my case as a student with a serious illness. During the meeting, I carefully explained my story, detailing how severe my symptoms were and the profound impact their actions had on my life. I asked them directly and sincerely why I had been treated this way.

My main concern during the meeting was to clearly convey that such an illness, though serious, is often temporary and does not reflect one's overall performance or abilities. I emphasized my competitive academic record, the success of previous research projects within the same lab, and the glowing recommendations I had received from other professors – including one that stated, *"He is an academically gifted student and can handle responsibility. I am confident he will become a successful and productive researcher."* Despite this, Dr. ι insisted that performing well during my Master's didn't guarantee success in my PhD. He firmly maintained that my perceived insufficient performance was due to my unsuitability for academia rather than understanding my illness as a temporary condition that impacted my work. His frustration was palpable, and at times during the meeting, he seemed visibly angry.

The conclusion of the meeting with Dr. ι was that ETH Zürich had made no mistakes; the system, in their view, was working as intended. They explained that my situation was simply a case of falling through the cracks, or as they put it, *"like Swiss cheese slices on top of each other, where the holes accidentally line up."* Miss μ even asked, *"What did you learn from this?"* – indicating, that I should improve in handling such situations better. Dr. ι mentioned they had recently held a mental health workshop, implying his awareness and sensitivity to such issues. He also stated that he had handled my case with the best interest of his lab in mind. Some of my former colleagues, aware of my story, confided that they felt uneasy, knowing something similar could happen to them. The difficult work environment had taken a toll on others' mental health as well, and I later learned I wasn't the only one dismissed under similar circumstances due to mental health struggles.

These results devastated me. Despite several meetings, I struggled to help supervisors and staff truly grasp the nature of mental health issues and how to address them. It breaks my heart to think that, had they understood better, my life could have taken a different course. What pains me even more is the realization that this lack of understanding means similar situations are likely happening and will continue to happen to other students as well.

Conclusion

During the first year of my doctoral studies at ETH Zürich, unforeseen personal life events and the toxic work environment created by my direct supervisor triggered an overwhelming and serious set of symptoms known as an episode of severe depression. This significantly impacted my work performance. Despite the challenges, I built coping mechanisms, sought professional help to manage the situation, and tried to do my best at work. However, my supervisor's reaction was dismissive, lacking both understanding and the ability to handle the situation appropriately. Instead of offering support, more pressure was added, worsening my condition to the point where hospitalization became unavoidable. Upon returning from sick leave, I was immediately dismissed, plunging me into an extremely difficult life situation and simultaneously causing every aspect of my life to collapse. This pushed me into a deep and long-lasting existential crisis, effectively creating a much larger problem than the illness itself. When I sought help from university organizations specifically designed to address such issues, I was met with similarly dismissive and, at times, even intimidating responses. I felt threatened and disregarded. This entire experience not only added significantly to my mental health challenges but also led to physical symptoms in the form of chronic stomach problems, deepening my existential crisis. All it would have taken to prevent this was a few months of unpaid, protected sick leave, along with an understanding of the seriousness, treatability, and temporary nature of my

illness, its impact on my performance, and the fact that it did not reflect my true abilities.

After this period, my view of ETH Zürich changed significantly. Before my Master's studies, I had prepared for years to get into the program. I saw ETH professors as idols and the university as a strong, competitive environment – perfect for enthusiastic, hard-working, and dedicated students like me eager to push the boundaries of science. I was extremely proud to be part of this community. Like any other student, I was unaware of the many similar incidents [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] and could never have imagined that the institution I had praised so highly could treat anyone this way. However, after my own experiences and hearing similar stories from other students, my perception shifted drastically. I can only see ETH now as a perfectly fertile ground for a toxic research culture to flourish, where the institution prioritizes maintaining a strong public image over actually providing quality supervision and a healthy work environment for its scientific staff. I believe many ETH professors adopted a Machiavellian philosophy as a driving principle [11]. They can abuse their power [15] and students in an unregulated, unchecked way, with few boundaries, responsibilities, or accountability set by the institution. This leaves early-career researchers vulnerable to exploitation by established and powerful professors.

Suggestions for students

I've gathered a set of suggestions based on my experience that could have made my struggle easier. I hope these insights will help others in similar situations. If you are a student, especially PhD or Postdoc on a payroll, facing mental health issues, physical illnesses, pregnancy, or any challenges affecting your work performance, the following advice may be useful. Remember, situations can escalate quickly, and there's often no safety net in place. Both your health and career are at serious risk if these issues are not addressed.

- Know your rights. Familiarize yourself with the relevant ordinances for PhD, Postdoc, or other employment contracts [16]. If necessary, consult a lawyer to ensure you take the right steps to protect yourself.
- If you have a short-term contract – most PhD contracts are renewed annually – do not assume it will be automatically extended. Consult with your supervisors about the renewal process and obtain written confirmation. Ensure this aligns with the current ordinances for PhD students [16]. Keep in mind that supervisors can choose not to renew your contract for various reasons, and you may not be protected. These contracts are designed in a way that protects the professors and the institution and not the students.
- Ensure that all communication between you and your supervisors is documented in writing (via email or paper), especially regarding any issues with health or

performance. Obtain written confirmation that they acknowledge the seriousness of your situation.

- If your performance is affected by your health and you are a PhD or Postdoc with an employment contract, it is crucial to consult a Swiss doctor to verify your condition. If necessary, take the initiative to reach out to Case Management directly [2].
- Prepare for the possibility of being dismissed. Start exploring alternative job opportunities early. If your contract ends and your supervisors choose not to renew it, you may find yourself in a precarious situation. Depending on your country of origin, your time in Switzerland may be limited, and the competition for jobs can be fierce. Have a contingency plan in place to navigate any challenging circumstances that may arise. I recommend reaching out to ETH's Career Center [17].
- If you feel you are not being treated well, consider reaching out to organizations such as AVETH [3], Respect ETH [4], or the local Ombuds Office [5] for support. Regardless, it's wise to prepare for the possibility of leaving the university and seeking new opportunities elsewhere.

Request directed to the leaders of ETH Zürich

Your institution is one of the most competitive in Europe and the World. This naturally makes students and early career researchers disposable since hundreds line up to fill someone's place. Adopting a turtle parenting strategy may seem reasonable. Instead of nurturing your students, you can throw them into deep waters. Some might drown, but enough will stay afloat. This makes supervision easier for you, while you can still maintain high-level research output. However, you are also a leading institution, a model for other universities and research labs. Ask yourself the question, do you really want to build an academic culture based on neglecting, exploitative, or sometimes even abusive supervisory practices?

Attitude towards mental health problems

Mental health issues in competitive academia, particularly at ETH, represent a significant and alarmingly growing concern [18, 19, 20, 21]. Navigating these challenges is incredibly difficult, even though effective treatments are available and many of these conditions are treatable. However, mental health issues are often met with distant fear or outright dismissal. As a leading institution, ETH cannot afford to overlook these problems.

When supervisors systematically mistake common and often serious mental health issues for laziness or incompetence and treat struggling students as problematic or unfit for academia, they can unintentionally inflict lasting harm on both the student's health and their career development. Frustration and disregard for these challenges only exacerbate the situation, often leading to severe consequences. Many mental health challenges are treatable,

yet they place people in a vulnerable state. Offering support or reasonable solutions, rather than neglect and blame, can mean the difference between a swift recovery and a successful career or an inescapable downward spiral. It seems deeply unjust that, after years of high performance, someone's life could collapse due to a temporary illness – a period of vulnerability that could have been mitigated with a little bit of understanding and the simple provision of a few months of unpaid medical leave. Is it fair to dismiss students simply because they are perceived as weak or problematic, knowing there are many others ready to take their place? Would the same treatment be applied if a doctoral student became pregnant or was diagnosed with cancer?

I propose an alternative approach that fosters an academic culture where common mental health issues can be discussed openly and addressed as a community with institutional support and protection. Academia challenges our mental health. Nearly 50% of ETH students are estimated to experience symptoms caused by mental distress, and about 1/3 of students deal with more severe mental health difficulties [18]. These challenges should be recognized as common and potentially serious but also temporary and treatable. I believe supervisors play a crucial role in supporting their students, helping them reach their full potential despite any difficulties they encounter along the way. Institutions, in turn, have a responsibility to offer solutions in tough situations, ensuring quality supervision and cultivating a healthy work culture for all employees. I believe that despite the hardships, people suffering from mental health problems also have a place in the academic community.

Misconduct beyond mental health

The issue I'm addressing extends beyond the health problems of early career researchers and students. Moreover, my experience is not an isolated case but rather a symptom of a much larger systemic problem. Throughout my interactions with several high-level staff members, I repeatedly encountered dismissive and ineffective responses, revealing a troubling pattern in the institution's approach to handling these issues. There seem to be dozens of similar cases where professors overstepped their boundaries and abused their power [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 22, 14, 12, 13], leading to severe, long-lasting, and in some instances, even fatal consequences [23, 24]. In fact, a survey on doctoral student supervision conducted by AVETH in 2018 showed that around 24% of PhD students experience abuse of power by their professors or supervisors [15]. Issues such as bullying, misconduct, sexual harassment, and discrimination frequently arise at ETH Zürich. Student reports seem to agree on one thing: the university dismissed their complaints and did nothing to help them; they felt abandoned by the institution.

Following a scandal after a similar incident [10], ETH President Joël Mesot in 2019 acknowledged: *"ETH as an institution has also made mistakes. When concrete reports were made, escalation channels did not always operate effi-*

ciently, and communication with the parties concerned was not always ideal during the subsequent proceedings." He also announced measures aimed at improving leadership and supervision quality to avoid similar cases in the future. ETH Rector Sarah Springman stated: *"With these measures, along with others derived from best practices in our academic departments and other universities around the world, we will raise the supervision of doctoral students to a new level."* She added: *"Regular feedback sessions between doctoral students and supervisors would detect and address problems early on, and a leadership program for professors would enhance leadership skills through coaching."* Additionally, they claimed that ETH would go beyond standard practices by increasing the number of ombudspersons and trusted intermediaries and revising the process for handling reports and complaints.

However, based on my personal experience – starting my doctorate in 2021 – and new scandals surfacing this year [12, 25] – including a petition [25] signed by over a 1000 people – these promised reforms have failed miserably to address the underlying issues in ETH's academic culture.

Public image and reality

Based on my experience and the significant number of aforementioned cases of misconduct and bullying, I believe it is safe to say: there seems to be a considerable gap between the image ETH projects in the media, social media, and other promotional materials [26, 27, 28, 29, 30], and the reality students in similar cases had experienced [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 22, 14, 12, 13]. The university seems to prioritize preserving its public image over creating a genuinely healthy academic environment. When instances of mistreatment arise, there is a tendency to sweep these issues under the rug rather than address them with effective solutions. Promises of protection and support often fall short in practice, leaving many students feeling isolated and unsupported. As a powerful institution, ETH can sustain this approach, as students typically have little recourse to defend themselves. Yet, these underlying issues will persist, and sooner or later, they will require serious attention.

Professors at ETH wield significant power, and in cases of conflict, they can abuse this power to pose a real threat to a student's career development and health. As a result, most students involved in similar situations remain silent, fearing that speaking out could harm their future careers or may even result in lawsuits. Powerless students often have no meaningful way to seek protection or have their voices heard, leaving them feeling isolated or threatened. Their cases mostly remain hidden, allowing the underlying issues to persist unresolved. While ETH offers avenues for support, such as AVETH, Respect ETH, and the Ombuds Office, etc..., these organizations lack the authority to enforce real consequences or hold individuals accountable in cases of conflict, abuse, discrimination, or unjust treatment. Since these incidents usually remain hidden, the university's public image remains unaffected.

This makes addressing such issues extremely challenging due to a psychological phenomenon known as confirmation bias [31]. When a student's experience contradicts the well-known reputation and image of an established institution like ETH, the story becomes less believable. People have a natural tendency to dismiss new information that contradicts long-held perceptions. As a result, hundreds of such cases can be ignored before the truth is finally acknowledged.

Many talented students are eager to start or build their careers by joining ETH Zürich, naturally drawn by its exceptional ranking and reputation. Most assume that this prestige guarantees quality supervision and mentorship along with a supportive and protected work environment. But if these students knew that they might end up cornered in an abusive work environment, or that some professors might derail their careers instead of fostering them, would they still choose ETH? In my case, for instance, hearing my story led some friends – potentially talented doctoral candidates – to reconsider pursuing a PhD at ETH Zürich. What message are cases like mine sending? If prospective students were fully informed, would they still choose ETH over other universities? While ETH is highly ranked, other institutions may offer better support, stronger protections, and healthier work cultures. As Dr. λ put it, *"there are other universities too."* Here's an example of a philosophy from another institution – one I won't name – that I truly admire and see them wholeheartedly committed to: *"*** views health-care and wellness as critical, as good employee health enhances preparedness for the demands of working life. Health is not only personal but a shared resource that is crucial to the organization's performance."* How long can ETH Zürich remain competitive and attract top students without actively and efficiently addressing issues related to ensuring quality supervision and maintaining a healthy and protected work environment?

Quality control of supervision

Lack of quality control for supervisors can lead to mismanagement, toxic behaviors, and serious impacts on both research performance and student well-being. My experience exemplifies this issue: beyond my illness, Dr. α 's behavior significantly affected my health, my work performance, and the outcomes of many similar projects overseen by her. Later, I learned that numerous students had struggled with her supervision, which visibly affected the research quality in the lab.

In cases of performance issues within a research project, the university should not place blame solely on students. Instead, it should take responsibility for ensuring the quality of supervision. Since supervisors hold considerable power over their students, they also bear greater responsibility due to their control over research outcomes. Even the most talented students may struggle under poor supervision, while those facing challenges can flourish with effective mentorship. Quality supervision is essential for successful research projects and a

healthy work environment.

Quality supervision unlocks students' potential – something they cannot always achieve alone. By nurturing your students, you empower them to generate more creative and innovative ideas, leading to new scientific discoveries. Studies show that pressure stifles creative potential [32], and creative problem-solving is essential for scientific advancement. A system that tolerates pressuring and abusive supervision effectively blocks the potential of many students, ultimately impacting the institution's scientific contributions and competitiveness.

Early-career researchers and students are the backbone of academia. I urge the leaders of ETH Zürich to recognize the benefits of humane treatment, fairness, and compassion toward them. Take evaluations of supervisors seriously, offering guidance for improvement to ensure not only high research output but quality supervision. Provide genuine, balanced protection for students against abusive professors, enforcing responsibility and accountability for supervisory practices. Don't let students feel abandoned or cornered in difficult situations. You depend on them as much as they depend on you.

Acknowledgements

I want to extend my heartfelt thanks to my family, girlfriend, friends, therapists, and doctors for the incredible support they provided during my most challenging times. Without them, I might not be here today. I will forever be grateful.

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